

AUTONOMIC HEALING OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A microencapsulated self-healing system was incorporated into a woven S2 glass reinforced epoxy composite using a hand lay-up technique. A testing protocol based on compression after impact reveals significant (and impact-energy-dependent) recovery of compressive properties in self-healing panels with low-velocity impact damage.

Keywords: self-healing materials, polymer-matrix composites, impact damage, compression after impact

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites with polymeric matrices have found many uses in structural applications due to their high specific strength and stiffness. Despite However, they are particularly prone to damage from out-of-plane impact events. Delaminations, in particular, pose a serious issue because they can significantly reduce compressive strength [1, 2] and grow in response to fatigue loading [3]. Adding to the problem, impact damage can be subsurface or barely visible, necessitating the use of expensive and time-consuming non-destructive inspection [1]. Even if damage is located, the many repair techniques that have been proposed or are currently practiced [4, 5] can be time-consuming, complicated, and require unhindered access.

An alternative solution to manual repair is the employment of self-healing materials. In particular, White and coworkers have demonstrated a system based on microencapsulated healing agent for repairing damage in polymeric matrices [6]. The autonomic nature of this approach eliminates the need for external damage detection and repair. Monotonic fracture testing [7, 8] and fatigue tests [9, 10] were conducted on polymer composites without fiber reinforcement, demonstrating significant recovery of mechanical properties. In further work, Kessler et al. successfully incorporated the self-healing system into a fiber-reinforced composite and demonstrated recovery of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness [10, 11].

The current study represents the first attempts to demonstrate autonomic self-healing of low-velocity impact damage in fiber-reinforced composites. For this study self-healing functionality was integrated in a conventional woven glass-reinforced epoxy composite based on the system described by White et al. [6] and later modified by Rule et al. [12]. Autonomic repair of impact-induced matrix damage is investigated using a crack marking technique and direct observation of healed material. Mechanical recovery is demonstrated using a compression-after-impact (CAI) testing protocol. In addition, impact energy and lateral pressure are used to vary damage volume/separation to assess its effect on healing performance.

MATERIALS

Self-Healing Components

Distilled endo-DCPD filled microcapsules were manufactured by in situ poly(urea-formaldehyde) microencapsulation using the method described by Brown *et al.* [13]. Two different size ranges (35 μm and 125 μm number average diameter) of microcapsules were employed to promote both even distribution of microcapsules and delivery of adequate amounts of DCPD healing agent to crack planes.

Wax-protected catalyst microspheres were made using a method similar to that described by Rule et al. [12]. For this study, 10 wt% first generation Grubbs' catalyst (freeze-dried morphology [14]) was incorporated in paraffin wax microspheres. A 0.2 wt% aqueous polyvinyl alcohol (average M_w 85,000-124,000, 87-89% hydrolyzed, Sigma-Aldrich) solution was used instead of the 0.28 wt% aqueous poly(ethylene-co-maleic anhydride) solution used by Rule and coworkers. Plain paraffin wax microspheres were also fabricated for use in control specimens without self-healing functionality. Wax microspheres of 135 μm diameter were used in this study.

Composite Materials, Lay-up, and Curing

Composite panels for low-velocity impact were nominally $101 \times 101 \times 4$ mm and consisted of 4 plies of 24 oz/yd² 5×5 yarns/inch plain woven S2-glass fabric (Owens Corning Knytex SBA240F) in an Epon 862 and Epi-cure 3274 matrix (100:40 weight ratio). Self-healing (SH) panels were made with a 2:1 mass ratio of 35 μm to 125 μm DCPD-filled microcapsules, as well as catalyst-containing wax microspheres of 135 μm average diameter. Three types of control panels were employed in this study. Plain composite panels (C-I) contained no self-healing components. A second set of controls (C-II) contained only microcapsules at a 2:1 mass ratio of 35 μm to 125 μm size ranges. A final set of controls (C-III) contained both microcapsules and plain wax microspheres. A summary of panel compositions can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of composite panel types.

Panel Type	DCPD Microcapsules	Wax Microspheres
C-I	none	none
C-II	35 μm and 125 μm	none
C-III	35 μm and 125 μm	plain 135 μm
SH	35 μm and 125 μm	10 wt% Grubbs', 135 μm

The samples were cured at room temperature for 24 hours under compaction pressure, followed by 48 hours at 35°C with no pressure applied. Plain composite panels were compacted with 4.8 kPa pressure, while panels containing microcapsules and/or wax microspheres were compacted with 95.8 kPa of pressure, yielding a final panel thickness of approximately 4 mm and a fiber content of approximately 33% for all panels. The concentrations of self-healing components in the composite panels were estimated to be 0.13 g/cm³ DCPD microcapsules and 0.039 g/cm³ wax microspheres (0.0039 g/cm³ Grubbs' catalyst).

TESTING AND CHARACTERIZATION

Low-Velocity Impact Testing

Impact testing was conducted on an Instron Dynatup 8200 instrumented drop weight impact tester with the sample circularly clamped (76 mm diameter) and a spherically shaped impact head of 25.4 mm radius of curvature. Samples were impacted with incident impact energies ranging from 0 to 45.1 J. All impacted self-healing panels were given 48 hours to heal before further testing. SH panels were healed under ambient conditions, room temperature and no lateral pressure.

Damage Imaging and Quantification

Panels were sectioned through the point of impact into four quarters for imaging. Delaminations and matrix cracks exposed on the cross-section surface were marked by a fluorescent dye penetrant (Zyglol ZL-37) using a technique demonstrated by Kuboki et al. [15]. Figure 1a shows a typical image of highlighted damage under UV illumination. For each panel, four separate images were obtained, one for each sectioning cut.

The total crack length per imaged edge was measured to quantify the degree of damage. First, cracks were manually traced with a pencil tool in Adobe Photoshop CS2. The resulting images were thresholded to yield just the crack tracings, which were in turn skeletonized using a Fovea Pro photo analysis plugin (Fig. 1b). Finally, the total length of the skeleton was then computed using the same plug-in software.

Figure 1: (a) Image of fluorescently marked cracks under UV illumination. (b) Skeletonization of marked cracks.

Compression after Impact

Compression after impact was used to measure the residual compressive strength (RCS) of composites with impact damage. A CAI fixture was designed to accommodate the 101 mm \times 101 mm panels based on the standard CAI geometry. All panels underwent compression testing using a MTS 812 hydraulic test frame coupled with a Instron 8800 controller at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. Panels, both damaged and undamaged, were loaded until complete compressive failure across the width of the sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Damage Characterization

Self-healing panels impacted at 45.1 J show a 51% decrease in total crack length per imaged edge when compared to the corresponding C-III controls (Fig. 2). Plain composite panels (C-I) and microcapsule-only panels (C-II) were also tested to observe the effects of self-healing components on damage resistance. As shown in Figure 2, there is a negligible increase in total crack length per imaged edge when plain panels are compared to microcapsule-only panels, indicating that the addition of the microcapsules does not significantly reduce impact damage resistance. However, C-III panels show a significant jump in total crack length per edge, suggesting that the combination of wax microspheres and DCPD microcapsules reduces damage resistance markedly. In contrast, self-healing panels exhibit dramatically smaller crack length per imaged edge when compared to all three controls.

Closer inspection of through-damage cross-sections of self-healing panels reveals poly-DCPD-filled delamination and transverse cracks, as well as unhealed sections (Fig. 3a). Healed delaminations are marked by a trail of poly-DCPD-filled microcapsules that have ruptured onto the crack plane. C-III controls, which lack catalyst, do not show evidence of rebonded crack or delamination faces (Fig. 3b).

Figure 2: Total crack length per imaged edge for plain (C-I), microcapsule-only (C-II), microcapsule and microsphere (C-III), and self-healing (SH) composite panels impacted with 45 J. Error bars are \pm one standard deviation.

Figure 3: Optical micrographs of cross-sections of (a) a partially healed section of delamination in a self-healing panel impacted with 45 J and (b) a section of unhealed delamination in a C-III non-healing control panel impacted with 45 J.

Compression-after-Impact Results

The residual compressive strength (RCS) as a function of incident impact energy is plotted in Figure 4 for self-healing and C-III controls. Both types of panels indicate a threshold impact energy below which no drop in RCS is detected. Self-healing panels show a higher threshold energy than C-III panels, nearly double that of C-III panels. In both types of panels, a reduction in RCS occurs with increasing impact energy, but for self-healing panels this drop-off in performance appears to be faster.

The model developed by Caprino [16] for the strength of notched composite panels has also been generalized for compression after impact [17] and can be used to fit experimental data. RCS, σ_r , is related to impact energy, U , by the power law

$$\frac{\sigma_r}{\sigma_0} = \left(\frac{U_0}{U} \right)^\beta, \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 is the undamaged compressive strength and U_0 is the threshold impact energy. For analyzing the data in this study, σ_0 was taken as the average compressive strength of all undamaged C-III panels. The parameters U_0 and β were obtained by fitting the experimental data to Equation 1. For C-III controls, panels impacted with 17.8 J or more were used, while for SH panels, panels impacted with 22.2 J or more were used. Because six of eight SH panels impacted with 17.8 J healed to at least 97% of the average undamaged C-III RCS, the SH panels impacted at this energy were assumed to be below the threshold impact energy and were not included in the fit. The threshold impact energy, U_0 , for self-healing panels (19.7 J) is found to be almost twice that of C-III panels (10.7 J).

Figure 4: Residual compressive strength (RCS) for non-healing control panels (C-III) and self-healing panels (SH) versus nominal incident impact energy. Error bars are \pm one standard deviation. Also plotted is a fit to RCS based on a model from [17].

In a study on the effect of microcapsules size on healing performance, Rule and coworkers [18] found that healing efficiency in tapered double cantilever beam specimens is reduced with decreasing amounts of delivered healing agent. This result was attributed to inadequate filling of the crack volume with healing agent. Likewise, the better recovery of RCS at lower impact energies is likely the result of decreased damage volume and separation. Optical images of cross-sections of impacted C-III composites reveal that delamination separation increases with increasing impact energy. Figure 5 shows examples of the largest delamination separations observed for C-III

panels impacted with 45.1 J and 17.8 J. C-III panels impacted with 45.1 J can have delamination separations on the order of 100 μm , whereas the largest delamination separations seen in C-III panels impacted with 17.8 J are approximately 35 μm . For the case of 17.8 J, more complete damage filling is possible, resulting in better healing performance.

Figure 5: Examples of the largest delamination separations seen in C-III panels impacted with (a) 45.1 J and (b) 17.8 J.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides visual and mechanical confirmation of self-healing of low-velocity impact damage in composite materials. A significant decrease in crack length is observed when comparing impacted self-healing panels to corresponding impacted control panels. It is also observed that the addition of microcapsules to the matrix of the composite has little effect on impact damage resistance, while the additional incorporation of wax microspheres, increases impact damage considerably. A protocol based on CAI demonstrates that self-healing panels recover residual compressive strength. Self-healing functionality increases the threshold impact energy by nearly twofold compared to non-self-healing controls.

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